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HOW TO CREATE NEW LANGUAGE LEARNING HABITS IN YOUTH.

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Abstract: Today, it is very important for everyone to know foreign languages. The world becoming increasingly globalized and bilingual is not just hotness is becoming the need of the hour. How to learn foreign languages with others a life focused on learning to truly communicate and connect with them skill. Why should we learn foreign languages? Why am I learning foreign languages now? I will write about the reasons why it is necessary to study

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Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, in the natural environment, that is, in the family, among the public or can be acquired in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Languages in our time when international relations are on the rise knowledge, especially multilingualism, is of great importance. Study in our country students usually study three languages. These languages are special are managed by names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. Mother tongue It is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. Second when talking about language, it means brothers and sisters of other nationalities, it is considered as the language of neighbors. If you're already bilingual or multilingual, speak to your child in the languages you already speak as soon as you can. Continuous exposure introduces the concept of multilingualism to children early on in life and in a very natural way. An early start to language learning is also helpful because it makes it easier for kids to pick up new language skills later in life – they will think of multilingualism as natural, have a basis in the sounds and flow of the new language, and even give them a basic foundation for learning a new language from scratch.

A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western Europe in our republic (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) languages is being taught. These languages are included in the

curricula of educational institutions. The process of teaching three languages is different. Mother tongue and second language are natural in a situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language is mainly takes place in the lesson under the guidance of the teacher. Among the three languages, learning a foreign language and teaching differs sharply in certain aspects. This, in turn, is relevant requires the use of foreign language teaching technology. Foreign language teacher methodology the language experience gained by the student through thorough assimilation of scientific achievements he gets to know the norm clearly and to improve it further. Foreign languages effective teaching requires knowledge of its methodology.

In addition to the passive learning they are exposed to if you speak the language at home, a little active learning can go a long way – and can set the stage for a positive relationship with language learning for life.

With older children, more conscious practice is essential and as a parent you can do a lot to support the development of healthy learning habits.

Practice really does make perfect, so making sure your child sits down to practice writing, improve their comprehension and review class notes regularly is key. Memory is aided by repetition and children's learning habits are proven to respond well to structure.

If you can plan an hour or so into every day, it'll sink in far faster than if they only connect with the language once or twice a week. Have you heard about the guy who learned to speak a foreign language in one day? That's because a story like that doesn't exist. In language learning, we often find ourselves looking for the silver bullet — how to learn a language quickly and with minimal effort. Yet we are always met with the harsh truth that learning another language takes time and hard work. However, effective language learning doesn't have to be a painful, tedious process. Done right, it can be a thrilling adventure that can take you to places you never imagined and introduce you to people that can change your life. Allow us to show you how.

Do you remember everything you learned about the Roman Empire in history class? What about the process of chemical bonding that you learned about in science class? Unless your career or daily life require this knowledge, the answer to both of these questions is probably “no.”

Naturally, the same logic holds true for language learning. If you are not frequently and consistently engaging with the language you want to learn, you will most likely fall victim to “the forgetting curve”.

A person begins to acquire communication skills from childhood. But after growing up, not everyone can establish communication as needed. Pedagogical profession, by its nature, belongs to the professions of the "human-human" type and that is why the ability to communicate is the leader for a pedagogue, is considered one of the important professional skills. The pedagogue takes with the students children's interest in the subject depending on their communication and behavior, that is, learning motives are formed. Pedagogical communication method students by subject knowledge, effectiveness of skills, interpersonal relationship affects the culture, has a unique moral-psychological effect in the educational process creates climate. Communication is an important condition for the socialization of a person is considered Here it is necessary to know what pedagogical communication actually is considered.

A number of personal qualities necessary for the culture of pedagogical communication include honesty, openness, self-control, demandingness, sincerity, patience, endurance, tact. The teacher is only himself not only the communicative skills, but also the students' interculturality should form communication. The teacher is good at student psychology it is necessary to know their social views and socialization processes will be done. It should be noted that pedagogical, intercultural communication success or failure according to the final result what method of treatment the pedagogue-teacher chooses and how to use it depends on being able to use it. The teacher does not only work during the lesson to be able to interest the students in the lesson process, to express their opinion freely should be taught.

In conclusion, knowing English is for every field representative is the key to new opportunities. One door if you know your field well, English language if you know, another door will open. Indeed, knowing a language opens the door to the whole world takes.

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